

STUDY ON THE BENDING BEHAVIOR OF LAMINATES CONNECTED BY RIVETS

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SUMMARY: A study with a numerical approach is conducted to investigate the post-buckling behavior of Laminates connected by rivets. However, the behavior of the laminate with a single rivet should be taken into consideration prior to solving the macro behavior of the laminate with several rivets. This study majorly focuses on the bending behavior and the interaction between the rivet and the laminate as the paperation. The finite element software ABAQUS is used to inspect the 3-D contact behavior between two contacting surface sets, the laminate and the rivet, and, the laminate and the stiffener. The user subroutine, UMAT is used to modify the engineering constants and the stresses when the elements are identified as failing. Several parameters are considered. As a result, it shows that the stacking sequence has great influence on the behavior.

KEYWORDS: post-buckling, contact behavior, failure criterion, rivets, laminates

INTRODUCTION

Due to the high specific strength, rigidity and corrosion resistance, composite materials have been widely utilized in airplanes, ships, automobiles and other respects. Among the various structures, laminates are a basic type. The flush-head rivets are frequently used on them for force transmission and the smoothness of the flowlines. When the laminates and the rivets act in union, and are subjected to various loadings, the behavior of the joint is rather complicated. The structure may buckle easily on the ground that the strength between the laminae is not high enough. While the deflection is increasing, local fracture is expanding around the rivets. Then, the efficiency will go downhill rapidly and cause the total failure of the structure. Therefore, the study on the behavior of the laminates connected by rivets should be practiced thoroughly.

There have been several research reports on this top since 1970. Most investigations restricted the analyses to 2D problem with a simple geometry, such as Ref. [1] to [2] and [4] to [5]. They determined the stress distribution and the failure strength of various modes. However, 3D analysis is imperative because the the interlaminar strength has great influence over the behavior. Few documents, Ref. [3], [6] and [7] had the analyses about structures of 3D geometries with in-plane deformations. However, these analyses treated the rivet or the bolt as a rigid body. The contact between the rivet and the laminate in radial direction was modified as constraints. In this way, the elastic characteristic of the rivet was not considered. Neither was buckling and post-buckling. Ref. [8]~[10] had the analyses on the buckling behavior of laminates jointed by several rivets. In these documents, the rivets are only modeled as elastic

nodes instead of an elastic body. Hence, it's obvious that the post-buckling behavior of laminates jointed by rivets still needs further research.

To this end, the present study uses the finite element software, ABAQUS, and models the rivet as an elastic body. The contact pressure and the stress distribution of the structure can be obtained. With user subroutine, UMAT, the engineering constants and stresses will be modified by proper failure criterion and the nonlinear behavior is understood.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Composite laminated sheets are often jointed with metal stiffener by rivets as in Fig. 1. When the structure is subjected to in-plane loadings, the laminates may buckle and the area around the rivet will fail besides the fracture in the center of the laminate. To understand the local behavior, the area surround by dashed lines is extracted as the model to be analyzed. The loading changes to be out-of-plane to model the deformation and displacement in z -direction. The coordinate system and the geometry are shown in Fig. 2. The mesh, dimension and the dimension of the rivet are shown in Fig. 3. The prescribed displacement (h') is along side BC. Because of symmetry, face ABFE, HDCG and BCGF are symmetrical planes. D is the diameter of the rivet root. The length of the laminate is $L_t=15D$; the half length of the face plate of the stiffener is $L_b=5D$; e is the distance from the center of the rivet to the nearer edge and equals to $3D$; w is the width of the plate and also the rivet pitch. The laminate is made of the material T300/976. The rivet is aluminum alloy. The material constants are as table 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. laminate jointed with the stiffener by rivets under in-plane loadings

Fig. 2. the geometry of the structure

Fig. 3. finite element mesh and the dimension

Table 1: The material properties of the rivet and the stiffener

Aluminum Alloy	E(GPa) : 70	ν : 0.32
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Table 2: The material properties of the composites

laminate : T300/976			
Engineering constants		strength	(MPa)
E_1 (GPa)	1.393E2	X_t	1.517E3
E_2 (GPa)	9.722	X_c	1.593xE3
E_3 (GPa)	9.722	Y_t	4.454E1
ν_{12}	0.29	Y_c	2.530E2
ν_{13}	0.29	Z_t	4.454E1
ν_{23}	0.29	S_{12}	1.069E2
G_{12} (GPa)	5.585	S_{13}	1.069E2
G_{13} (GPa)	5.585	S_{23}	1.069E2
G_{23} (GPa)	3.447		

CONTACT PROBLEM

Contact behavior is highly nonlinear. Here the contact includes the contact between the rivet and the laminate along the rivethole, and the laminate and the face plate of the stiffener. It is not modeled as prescribed constraints but 2 contact pairs in ABAQUS, meaning that the a contact set has 2 contact surfaces which belonged to separate contact elements. The contact behavior is confined to only small sliding. The originally matched contact nodes will stay close and won't contact with the nodes of the other elements. The friction is also neglected in this study.

FAILURE CRITERIA AND SIMULATIONS

In the present study, the 3D Hashin failure criterion and Ye delamination are adopted in the user subroutine, UMAT, as a supplement for ABAQUS and prediction of the failure of the elements . Let $X_t, X_c; Y_t, Y_c, Z_t, ; S_{12}, S_{23}, S_{13}$ denote the corresponding strengths. The failure criteria may be described as follows:

(a) Fiber Breakage

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{11} \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

$$|\sigma_{11}| \geq X_c \quad \sigma_{11} < 0 \quad (2)$$

The Young's modulus E_1 , Poisson ratio $\nu_{12}, \nu_{21}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{31}$, shear modulus G_{12}, G_{13} , stress components σ_{11}, σ_{12} and τ_{13} are all reduced to 0 within the damaged element of the layer for fiber failure.

(b) Matrix Failure

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{S_{23}^2}\right) \cdot (\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}) + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_c}\right) \left[\left(\frac{Y_c}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 - 1 \right] + \frac{1}{S_{23}} (\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}) + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} < 0 \quad (4)$$

The Young's modulus E_2 , Poisson ratio $\nu_{12}, \nu_{21}, \nu_{23}, \nu_{32}$, shear modulus G_{12}, G_{23} , stress components σ_{22}, τ_{12} and τ_{23} are all reduced to 0 within the damaged element of the layer for matrix failure.

(c) Delamination

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{33} \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{33} < 0 \quad (6)$$

The Young's modulus E_3 , Poisson ratio ν_{23} , ν_{32} , ν_{13} , ν_{31} , shear modulus G_{23} , G_{13} , stress components σ_{33} , τ_{13} and τ_{23} are all reduced to 0 within the damaged element of the layer for delamination.

USER SUBROUTINE: UMAT

ABAQUS has provided a very complete material library. However, in the failure analysis, although ABAQUS has various kinds of criteria, the material properties and stresses cannot be modified within ABAQUS itself. Therefore, ABAQUS provides the flexibility for the users to write user subroutines to modify the materials. In the present study, UMAT is used to modify the values of the engineering constants and the stresses and calculate the stiffness matrix. Several verifications are needed to make sure it is available.

RESULTS

There are several parameters designed to evaluate the influence on the structure. They are the stacking sequence, the arrangement of the rivet, the stiffness of the stiffener, the head angle of the rivet and. In the present study, the prescribed displacement when failure happened is higher than the plate thickness. Therefore, the large deformation theory should be applied.

The Stacking Sequence

In the following study, the stacking sequence used is layer 4, the arrangement is taken as single line of rivet, the stiffener is elastic and the head angle of the rivet is 100. When one parameter is discussed, there will be 2 options for the parameter, but the others stay as above.

The relations between the reaction force (Rf) and h' are shown in the figures below. Fig. 4 shows the influence of the stacking sequence when the total number of layers is 24. Layup 4 is [(0/45/90/-45)₃]s while layup 5 is set-up as [(90/45/0/-45)₃]s. In Fig. 4, it's observed that the initial fracture starts when the prescribed displacement is raised to 1.2 to 1.4mm. The initial fracture of layup 4 begins later than layup 5. The slope of layup 4 is higher than layup 5, which means layup 4 has better strength. When final fracture happens, the load that the structure sustains goes down rapidly. In Fig. 4, it's also found that the final fracture of layup 4 happens earlier on the ground that layup 5 is easier to bend so that fractures later. From the computed results, the 0°, ±45° laminates are weaker and thus fracture earlier than the 90° laminate.

Fig. 4 The R_f - h' relation under the parameter - stacking sequence

Fig. 5 The R_f - h' relation under the parameter - arrangement of the rivets

The Arrangement of the Rivet

There are several arrangements in the real situation. Here, 2 types of arrangements are considered. The stacking sequence here is layup 4. When the constraint along the ADHG surface is symmetric to the x - z surface, it's the double line case. When the boundary is free along ADHG, it's the single line case. From Fig. 5, we can see that the single line case has weaker strength and endures lower loading.

The Stiffness of the Stiffener

The material properties of the stiffener also effects the behavior of the structure. Therefore the stiffener is modeled as both rigid and elastic. When it's elastic, the material is taken as Aluminum alloy. In Fig. 6, it can be seen the structure with the elastic stiffener will have lower strength but sustain higher loading.

Fig. 6 The R_f - h' relation under the parameter - the material of the stiffener

Fig. 7 The R_f - h' relation under the parameter - the head angle of the rivet

The Head Angle of the Stiffener

There are two frequently used head angles of rivets, 80° and 100° . The change of the head angle doesn't effect a lot according to Fig. 7. However, in the analysis, it's found that the fracture modes are quite different. The cases above and the structure with head angle of 100° mostly fracture around the hole, while with the rivet of head angle 80° , the structure fracture mostly near the area of prescribed displacement.

CONCLUSION

The stacking sequence is found to be very influential to the load sustaining ability of the laminate connected by the rivet. When the 0° lamina is placed closer to the surface instead of the 90° lamina, the high strength of the fiber will help the structure to have higer overall strength. The softer the stiffener is, the more flexible the structure is to deform. However, in the aspect of load sustaining ability and overall strength, the material of the structure and the head angle of the rivet don't influence the structure in great scale.

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